

The following provides an overview of neighbourhood assets and potential barriers/gaps for older adults. The features were identified through a structured assessment in May 2023. As such, this summary should be viewed as an overview of key features observed rather than an exhaustive list.

The majority of housing north of The Esplanade was comprised of newer condominium developments, whereas, south of The Esplanade is primarily co-operative housing buildings. The neighbourhood had several narrow parkettes that consisted of green space where individuals or families were walking. Regarding fitness activities, there were a small number of designated outdoor areas for sports, such as a basketball court and baseball field. Further, there were several private fitness facilities within the area. The neighbourhood had several main roads that were very busy with street traffic, bicycles, and people walking along the narrow sidewalks. There were also some designated bike lanes along some roads. Although walking and biking appeared to be the main modes of transportation for residents, bus routes were operating along some of the main roads and a streetcar line operating along King Street.

St. Lawrence appeared to be a vibrant neighbourhood with many accessible retail shops, restaurants, liquor and cannabis stores, entertainment venues, and tourist areas, such as the St. Lawrence Market. With many historical buildings and plaques throughout the area, there was also a sense of community pride regarding the neighborhood's history and character. The people walking in the neighbourhood were also observed to be ethnically diverse, with variable levels of mobility. Several people were also noted to have physical disabilities and used mobility aids. Regarding necessities, there were many grocery stores, pharmacies, and convenient stores. The largest grocery stores, No Frills and Metro, were at the East and West points of the St. Lawrence neighborhood. As the neighbourhood is a large area, this could pose an accessibility issue for some people. However, St. Lawrence Market is located at the heart of St. Lawrence which offers vendors that sell grocery items, including fresh produce and meat.

There appeared to be a socio-economic divide within the neighbourhood. Specifically, along Front Street and King Street, it was observed that the majority of the retail shops, restaurants, and cafes were newly developed and catered affluent individuals or groups. The buildings and shops south of The Esplanade were older, in comparison, and appeared to serve those of lower socio-economic status.

Map 1. Food sources identified in St. Lawrence

Map 2. Retail stores identified in St. Lawrence

Map 3. Services identified in St. Lawrence

Index of all services in St. Lawrence

Legend Number	Description
Education	
1	Aneesa Daycare
2	Downtown Alternative School
3	George Brown College - St. James Campus
4	Kaplan International Languages
5	Market Lane Jr and Senior Public School
6,7,8	St. Lawrence Co-Operative Day Care Inc.
9	St. Michael Catholic School
10	Toronto Public Library
Fitness/Recreation	
11	Altitude Athletic Training
12	Balanced Body Active Health Centre
13	BeHot Yoga Toronto
14	Body + Soul Fitness
15	F45 Training
16	MedX Precision Fitness
17	St. Lawrence Community Recreation Centre
Food Sources	
18	A&W Canada
19	Aroma Espresso Bar
20	Au Pain Doré
21	Balzac's Market Street
22	Big Pita
23	Bolets Burrito
24	Booster Juice
25	Bulk Barn*
26	Butter Chicken Roti
27	Chatime
28	Cluck Clucks Chicken & Waffles
29	Freshii
30	Karma's Kitchen
31	Khao Hakka
32	Market Street Catch
33	McDonald's
34	Metro*
35	Nari Sushi
36	Neo Coffee Bar
37	Pi Co.
38	Pizza Hut
39	Pizza Pizza
40	Popeyes Louisiana Kitchen
41	Presse Café
42	Pumpnickel's
43	RC Coffee Robo Cafe
44	Rocco's NOFRILLS Toronto*
45	Rooster Coffee House
46	St. Lawrence Cafe
47	St. Lawrence Market*
48	Starbucks
49,50,51	Subway
52	Tacorrito
53	Third Wave Coffee Inc.
54,55,56	Tim Hortons
*Grocery and/or whole food stores	
Restaurants	
57	Amano Trattoria
58	ARDO Restaurant
59	Aromatic Biryani
60	Bar St. Lo
61	Bellissimo Pizzeria & Ristorante
62	Biagio Ristorante
63	Bier Market
64	Biff's Bistro
65	Bindia Indian Bistro
66	Brash and Sassy Vodka Bar
67	Cantina Mercatto
68	CC Lounge and Whisky Bar
69	C'est What
70	Cora Breakfast and Lunch
71	Dukes Refresher
72	Fresh Kitchen + Juice Bar Front
73	Gabby's - King Street E
74	Goose Island Brewhouse Toronto
75	HOTHOUSE
76	imPerfect Fresh Eats
77	Le Papillon On Front
78	Oliver & Bonacini Café Grill
79	On the Rocks
80	P.J. O'Brien Irish Pub & Restaurant
81	Patrician Grill

- 82 [Petit Dejeuner](#)
 - 83 [Piano Piano Restaurant](#)
 - 84 [Playa Cabana](#)
 - 85 [Score on King](#)
 - 86 [Scotland Yard Pub](#)
 - 87 [Shoeless Joe's Sports Grill](#)
 - 88 [SukhoTHAI \(Wellington\)](#)
 - 89 [The Chefs' House](#)
 - 90 [The Corner Place](#)
 - 91 [The Jason George](#)
 - 92 [The Keg Steakhouse + Bar](#)
 - 93 [The Old Spaghetti Factory](#)
 - 94 [The Reservoir Lounge](#)
 - 95 [The Sultan's Tent and Cafe Maroc](#)
 - 96 [The WORKS Craft Burgers & Beer](#)
 - 97 [Uncle Tony's](#)
 - 98 [Victoria's Cafe](#)
 - 99 [Woods Restaurant & Bar](#)
- Health/Social Services**
- 100 [Centres D'accueil Heritage Les](#)
 - 101 [City Dental Toronto](#)
 - 102 [HealthCasa](#)
 - 103 [Main Drug Mart](#)
 - 104 [New Visions Toronto](#)
 - 105 [Nutrition Balance](#)
 - 106 [Older Women's Network](#)
 - 107 [Ontario Association of Children's Aid Societies](#)
 - 108 [Ontario Federation of Indigenous Friendships Centres](#)
 - 109 [Right To Play International](#)
 - 110 [Searchlight Recruitment, Inc.](#)
 - 111 [St Lawrence Pharmacy](#)
 - 112 [St. Lawrence Health Centre](#)
 - 113 [Step Up Massage & Rehab - Yonge & Wellington](#)
 - 114 [The Well Adjusted Chiropractic Centre](#)
 - 115 [Toronto Community Housing OJJ Office](#)
 - 116 [Toronto Public Service Learning Center](#)
 - 117 [Wellington Healthcare](#)
 - 118 [Yonge and Front Dental](#)

- Housing**
- 119 [Caroline Co-Operative](#)
 - 120 [Cathedral Court Co-Operative](#)
 - 121 [Harmony B Housing Co-Operative](#)
 - 122 [Marketview Housing Co-Operative](#)
 - 123 [Old York Tower](#)
 - 124 [PACE Independent Living](#)
 - 125 [Performing Arts Lodges Toronto](#)
 - 126 [Univeris Corporation Woodsworth Housing Co-operative Inc.](#)
 - 127 [Housing Co-operative Inc.](#)
- Parks**
- 128 [Berczy Park](#)
 - 129 [Market Lane Park](#)
 - 130 [David Crombie Park](#)
 - 131 [Parliament Square Park](#)
 - 132 [Princess Street Park](#)
 - 133 [Toronto Sculpture Garden](#)
- Protecting Services**
- 134 [Toronto Fire Station 333](#)
 - 135 [Toronto Police Services 51 Division](#)
- Religious Centres**
- 136 [Church in the City](#)
- Stores**
- 137 [ASK Computers](#)
 - 138 [BMO Bank of Montreal](#)
 - 139 [Boffi](#)
 - 140 [Canada Post](#)
 - 141 [Canna Cabana](#)
 - 142 [CIBC Branch](#)
 - 143 [Civilian House Of Cannabis](#)
 - 144 [Clutch Market](#)
 - 145 [Clutch Vape](#)
 - 146 [D & E Lake Ltd.](#)
 - 147 [Dollarama](#)
 - 148 [ergoCentric Showroom & Store](#)
 - 149 [Flatiron's Christmas Market](#)
 - 150 [Freedom Mobile](#)
 - 151 [Garrison Bespoke](#)
 - 152 [Gateway Newstands](#)
 - 153 [Ginkgo Floral Design](#)
 - 154 [Global Pet Foods Lower](#)
 - 155 [H&R Block](#)
 - 156 [Indochino](#)

157	International News	195	Curl Bar Beauty Salon
158	Kochi Stores	196	Esplanade Cleaners
159,160	LCBO	197	Hair Market Salon
161	Livia Diamonds	198	Jshair
162	Logan Kitchen and Bath	199	Lift Salon
163	Market Place	200	Market Cleaners
164	National Bank	201	My Hair Affair Salon Inc.
165	Nicholas Hoare	202	Nail Kandy
166	Noda Designs	203	Nova Cleaners on Jarvis/Esplanade
167	Office & Shop Furniture	204	Pink'C Nail Spa
168	Oopsie Deals Toronto Showroom	205	Sol'exotica
169	Pet Cuisine And Accessories	206	St Lawrence Cleaners
170	Pet Valu	207	St. Lawrence Super Coin Laundry
171,172	RBC Royal Bank	208	THE TEN SPOT
173	Red Rock Cannabis Store	209	Topcuts
174	Rexall	210	Valet Cleaners
175	Richie's Neighbourhood Store	211	Wellington Hair Salon
176	Risedesk (Office Furniture Store)	<hr/>	
177	Scotiabank	Entertainment	
178,179	Shoppers Drug Mart	212	Meridian Hall
180	St. Lawrence Pro Hardware	213	Albany Club
181	Stagioni	214	Banksy Street Art
182	TD Canada Trust Branch and ATM	215	Bar Cathedral
183	The Casablanca Tobacconist - Cigar Store	216	Beauchamp Art Gallery
184	The Optic Zone Inc	217	Canadian Opera Company
185	Time Square Convenience	218	Canadian Opera Company Theatre
186	Totally Toronto Art	219	Canadian Stage (Berkeley Street Theatre)
187	Trianon Design Ltd	220	Crosby Gallery
188	Value Buds	221	Kings and Queens Lounge
189	Waddington's Auctioneers & Appraisers	222	Feheley Fine Arts
190	Winners	223	Imagine Cinemas Market Square
191	Yahawa Fashion and Accessories	224	Joey & Toby Tanenbaum Opera Centre
<hr/>		225	Le Théâtre français de Toronto
OTHER		226	Maquette A Berkeley Event Venue
Personal Care Services		227	Museum of Illusions
192	Adam Barber Shop	228	St Lawrence Hall
193	B & M Salon	229	Young People's Theatre
194	Crown Cleaners		

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Ling. E., Kennedy, A. On behalf of the EMBOLDEN research team (2023). Environmental scan: St. Lawrence Market. URL: <https://emboldenstudy.mcmaster.ca/projects-results/>

Institute for Research on Aging

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Public Health Agency of Canada

Agence de la santé publique du Canada

St. Lawrence Market | CT 0015.00, 0016.00, 0013.01, 0017.00

Based on 2021 Census Data

CT Highlights

- Population** = 31,600
- Number of Homes** = 21,712
- Population Density** = 17,515/Km²
- 5-year Population change** = 27.3%

Age Distribution by Gender

\$62,275
Average Income (after tax)

11.7%
Unemployment Rate

Citizenship & Immigrant Population

Language Spoken at Home

English | 66.7%
Non-official Languages | 11.9%

Highest Certificate, Diploma or Degree

Neighbourhood Homes

Average monthly shelter costs

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Cite

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Data Source Statistics Canada. 20215350015.00, 5350016.00, 5350013.01 & 5350017.02 [Census tract]. www.statcan.gc.ca